

Generation Z Entrepreneurial Motivation in Adventure Tourism Enterprises in Kintamani Bali

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ABSTRACT: Research on Generation Z entrepreneurial motivation in adventure tourism businesses in Batur, Kintamani Bali, aims to describe the forms of entrepreneurial motivation for Generation Z in adventure tourism businesses in Kintamani, Bali. The priority of this research is that it is aimed at entrepreneurs or those who are planning to become entrepreneurs to find typology and motivation in developing a wider adventure tourism business in the Batur Kintamani area. Entrepreneurs must always have high motivation and a more positive self-concept in living their lives, even though the motivation and self-concept of each individual (entrepreneur) has different forms.

KEYWORDS: Adventure Tourism, Entrepreneurship, Generation Z

INTRODUCTION

Kintamani is a tourist area located in the northern part of Bali Island, Indonesia. This area is famous for its stunning natural views, especially views of Mount Batur and Lake Batur as well as Black Lava and Black Sand. The Batur Kintamani destination was named Batur Global Geopark by UNESCO in 2012. This area is famous for its stunning natural views, especially the views of Mount Batur and Lake Batur. Adventure tourism is tourism that involves any type of activity or adventure. This mainly relates to matters that involve risk, or require extensive planning. The Adventure Travel Trade Association defines it as tourism activities that include physical activity, cultural exchange, or tourism in nature.

Lately, many tourists are interested in doing adventure tourism. Adventure tourism in Kintamani includes Paragliding, Mount Batur ATV, Batur Jeep, Motocross Trip, Mount Batur Trekking, to white water rafting and cycling tours. Adventure tourism has become a large tourism industry in recent times. From this, many entrepreneurs from Generation Z are starting to get involved in the adventure tourism business in Kintamani.

The role of entrepreneurs in Bali has had many positive impacts, namely in the form of contributions in the transformation of communities with low incomes to higher incomes and from communities based on the primary sector to communities based on the service and technology sectors. In this way, Generation Z tourism entrepreneurs can help bring about rural development through solving the problem of unemployment and bringing economic development to the region. This research entitled Generation Z's entrepreneurial motivation in adventure tourism businesses in the Batur Kintamani area needs to be carried out to determine the characteristics and involvement of Generation Z in providing adventure tourism businesses. This is due to the increase in tourists visiting Batur Kintamani and the shift in tourists to carry out adventure activities.

Research on Generation Z's entrepreneurial motivation in adventure tourism businesses in Batur, Kintamani, Bali, aims to describe the forms of entrepreneurial motivation for Generation Z in adventure tourism businesses in Kintamani, Bali. The priority of this research is that it is aimed at entrepreneurs or those who are planning to become entrepreneurs to find typology and motivation in developing a wider adventure tourism business in the Batur Kintamani area.

According to Page et al (2006) adventure tourism or adventure tourism is various types of adventure activities or in its expanded sense, participants do not have to be experts or highly skilled participants to undertake adventure tourism. Adventure also denotes Action, not a passive experience and generally involves effort and commitment and requires mental and physical preparation or training. Adventure tourism or adventure tourism is a type of tourism that involves exploration or travel that contains risks, requires special skills and equipment as well as physical activity interactions with nature and/or culture (Kemenpar, 2018).

In the Adventure Tourism Development Index (ATDI) (2020), adventure tourism has important elements that form the overall experience (nature, activities and culture) to classify adventure tourism. Adventure tourism providers need to consider the components of the trip as individual ingredients but still in harmony, namely with the sequence of activities, duration and time given to reflect on the experience. Apart from that, "impact" is an important consideration for adventure tourism developers, namely by considering and planning for impact. Adventure tourists are motivated by longings and desires that influence how they consume and process their travel emotionally (Mackenzie & Goodnow, 2020). Tourists seek health both mentally and physically, new and unique experiences, physical or cultural challenges, which in the end often become transformational.

According to Janowski (2021), adventure tourism relies on three dimensional pillars, namely consumer, product and hybrid based. Consumer-based dimensions consist of psychological elements or intangible feelings evoked (e.g. sensation and excitement). Product-based dimensions are a mix of tangible and intangible features of the experience, regardless of the consumer's mindset (e.g. natural environment and physical activity). Finally, the hybrid dimension is influenced by product and consumer perceptions, skill level and/or behavior (eg risks, dangers and challenges).

According to Hasibuan (1996: 72), motivation is about how to encourage subordinates' passion for work, so that they work hard by giving all their abilities and skills to realize organizational goals. Robbins (1996: 198) defines motivation as the willingness to expend a high level of effort towards organizational goals which is conditioned by the ability of the effort to meet individual needs. According to Wahjosumidjo (1984: 50), motivation is a psychological process that reflects the interaction between attitudes, needs, perceptions and decisions that occur in a person.

METHODOLOGY

This research is qualitative research used by using 7 sources as key informants. Data collection was carried out by interviews and in Kintamani, Bali. This research uses a qualitative descriptive method, namely research that attempts to describe the phenomena or relationships between the phenomena studied systematically, factually and accurately (Kusmayadi, 2000:29; Nazir 1999:63).

In short, it can be explained that the data obtained from observation or direct observation is in the form of behavior related to the profession of the sources who are observed and interviewed. The data will be selected and selected according to the needs and objectives of this research. The data that has been collected will be transcribed first so that it becomes a form of data that is ready for analysis. Then, from the results of this clarification, all the data that has been selected will be analyzed and interpreted based on the theoretical basis that has been chosen to analyze and explain the data in detail so as to obtain analysis results that are in accordance with the problems that have been determined.

The research locations that will be used in this research are at several locations of Generation Z entrepreneurs spread across Kintamani, Bali.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Motivation can be understood as a state within individuals that causes them to behave in a way that ensures the achievement of a goal. Motivation explains how people behave as they do. The more entrepreneurs understand the behavior of organizational members, the more able they are to influence that behavior and make it more consistent with achieving organizational goals. Every entrepreneur has motivation, although in different forms. Motivation can be interpreted as a source of motivation for every entrepreneur to take action so that goals and hopes can be achieved.

The adventure tourism product offerings in Kintamani generally consist of 4 tourism product offerings, namely trekking tours to Mount Batur, ATV tours, JEEP tours and Trail Tours. Trekking tours are carried out by at least 12 organized tour operators and more than 150 individual guides. Adventure tourism offers with ATVs are carried out by tour operators such as Bali Aga, Batur Black Lava, and Batur Experience. Meanwhile, tourist product offerings using JEEP are offered by a number of operators such as KAJA, KAIT, Batur National Geographic, Batur Black Lava, NALA, Border, Mount Batur Adventure Bali Vulcano Jeep, Mount Batur Sunrise Trekking. Destination locations for adventure tourism are generally spread evenly throughout the region, such as Bukit Pole, Tabu, Bali Vulcano, Black Sand, Pine Forest.

Entrepreneurs who offer adventure tour packages in Kintamani generally make offering these tour packages a side job. They have main jobs or activities such as studying, as farmers, sand truck drivers, civil servants and other jobs in the tourist accommodation sector.

Generally, a number of reasons put forward by entrepreneurs in offering adventure tourism products are additional income, even more than their main job, pride in being able to earn more income and participate in the tourism business that is developing in the village, freedom to work, especially related to time, happiness in working in the field. This is because they seem more masculine, work with tourists who are generally beautiful, and are able to catch up with economic activity trends developing in their area.

The needs and goals model of motivation begins with an individual's feelings of need. These needs are then transformed into behavior that is directed to support the implementation of the goal behavior. The goal of goal behavior is to reduce a perceived need. Theoretically, goal supportive behavior and goal behavior are sustainable until the perceived need has been greatly reduced.

Yelon and Weinster (Hidayat, 2000) stated that behavior is the outer appearance of self-concept. The values adhered to by each entrepreneur will influence his motivation, the values obtained through the learning process both from the family, the social environment of society and the cultural environment in which he lives and develops. Thus, the high or low motivation of entrepreneurs in completing their tasks depends on how they perceive the values they adhere to. The more precise their perception of self-values can be predicted, the higher their motivation will be. This is in accordance with the opinion of Rokeach (1973) who states that a person's good perception of the values he adheres to can be used as a reference for selecting and developing his behavior. In fact, this perception can be a powerful driving force to develop enthusiasm for life, including achievement motivation (Yvon, 1997).

Considering that what entrepreneurs do largely depends on what motivates them, in this case entrepreneurs should be more aware of their self-concept so that if they have a positive self-concept then it is hoped that it will be developed, conversely if an entrepreneur has a negative self-concept then it is hoped that they can improve it. so that an entrepreneur can complete all the tasks received as well as possible.

Houston (Hidayat, 2000) in his research also said that a person's motivation is greatly influenced by his self-concept. A person's view or assessment of himself can be used as material to predict his motivation.

Entrepreneurs must always have high motivation and a more positive self-concept in living their lives, even though the motivation and self-concept of each individual (entrepreneur) has different forms. With motivation and self-concept, every task he receives, both personal and social tasks, as well as all previous needs and expectations can be achieved. In other words, the goals he aspires to can be achieved.

CONCLUSION

Based on these facts, it can be concluded that self-concept and motivation play an important role in the behavior displayed by a person, so it can also be concluded that the self-concept and motivation possessed by entrepreneurs have a big influence in the process of completing their tasks, even though self-concept and motivation are Entrepreneurs are different from one another.

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